

ON THE PREPARATION OF BACTERICIDALS FROM ORGANO-MERCURIALS. PART I

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Twenty-seven organo mercurials, derived from phenoxyacetic acid and phenylglycine-*o*-carboxylic acid of which 7 are known and 20 unknown, were prepared and analysed. Bactericidal activity of 22 of these compounds against *B. Coli* and *B. Para Typhosus B* was tested. All these compounds have been found to have a fair, and some quite high, germicidal potency.

Though about a dozen organo-mercury compounds like Mercurochrome, Merbaphen, Mersalyl, Metaphen and Mercurin are being widely used in medical practice, a systematic investigation of the simpler organo-mercurials does not seem to have been undertaken. It is proposed to describe in this and the following papers of this series, the preparation, properties and bactericidal action against *B. Coli* and *B. Para Typhosus B*, of a number of mercurated phenols, amines, urea, sulphanilamide derivatives and azo dyes, which have already been prepared and investigated in the laboratories of the Dacca University and of the Ravenshaw College, Cuttack. The first paper relates to a number of mercurated phenoxyacetic acids and phenylglycine-*o*-carboxylic acids, which were chosen in the belief that the protected phenolic and aminic groups in these molecules would lead to products of very low toxicity and of very high stability towards air and light, as well as towards body fluids.

In this paper, 22 aryloxy-fatty acids have been mercurated by standard methods, only seven of these are mentioned in the literature (D.R.P., 261299; 264,267; 261,575; vide also Goordon and Kipins, U.S.P., 1914, No. 2343,549). Their properties, and in some cases even their melting points, are not described. Only one method for their preparation is mentioned, whereas 4 methods of mercuration have been described in this paper. Five new mercury compounds of phenylglycine-*o*-carboxylic acid are also described, the products have been proved to be fairly stable to air and light and towards dilute acids and alkalis, very dilute H₂S and 1% NaCl solutions, which occur in the body fluids. Their solubility in dilute NaOH in the cold to give nearly neutral solutions (p_H 7 to 7.8) gives them an additional advantage in actual use.

TABLE I

Bactericidal action of mercury compounds of aryloxy-fatty acid series.

Temp. = 29. p_H = 7 to 7.6. After 12½ minutes.

No. of Compound.	Max. effective dilution against		No. of Compound.	Max. effective dilution against	
	<i>B. Coli</i> .	<i>B. Para Typhosus B</i> .		<i>B. Coli</i> .	<i>B. Para Typhosus B</i>
1	1: 10,000	1: 10,000	13	1: 50,000	1: 40,000
2	1: 15,000	1: 15,000	14	1: 45,000	1: 38,000
3	1: 15,000	1: 15,000	15	1: 50,000	1: 40,000
4	1: 15,000	1: 15,000	16	1: 45,000	1: 38,000
8	1: 45,000	1: 38,000	17	1: 70,000	1: 130,000
9	1: 40,000	1: 40,000	18	1: 20,000	1: 20,000
10	1: 40,000	1: 40,000	19	1: 40,000	1: 25,000
11	1: 60,000	1: 50,000	20	1: 65,000	1: 50,000
12	1: 75,000	1: 60,000			

TABLE II

*Bactericidal action of the mercury compounds of phenylglycine-o-carboxylic acid.*Temp. = 29°. $p_H = 7.5$.

No.	After X mins.	Maximum effective dilution against	
		B. Coli.	B. Para Typhosus B.
23	12½ mins	1 : 800,000	1 : 150,000
24	"	1 : 200,000	1 : 100,000
25	"	1 : 1000,000	1 : 500,000
	3 hrs	1 : 1000,000	—
26	12½ mins.	1 : 500,000	1 : 200,000
27	"	1 : 2000,000	1 : 700,000

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Preparation of Aryloxy-fatty Acids.—The general method of preparation of aryloxy-fatty acids from the appropriate phenol and chloro- or iodo-fatty acid (*J. Amer Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 53, 304; 1943, 65, 1555) was adopted with a slight modification. The aryloxy-acids obtained as oils (which soon solidified) were directly crystallised from hot water, until no further change could be seen in their melting points. By this process of purification, the substances obtained were pure enough, as was established from their equivalent weight determinations (0.1 g. of the acid, dissolved in 10 c.c. of alcohol, was titrated against *N/10*-NaOH solution) and a comparison of the m.p. with those given in the literature (Table III). In general, these melting points obtained were similar to those previously reported. In some cases somewhat higher melting points were obtained.

TABLE III

Acid.	M.p. (obs.)	M.p. (lit.)	Equivs. (obs.)	Equivs. (calc.)
1. Phenoxy-acetic acid		96-97°, 98-99.1°	152.3	152
2. <i>o</i> -Cresoxy-		151-52°, 156.8-157.4°	167	166
3. <i>m</i> -Cresoxy-		102-103°, 103-103.5°	167.56	166
4. <i>p</i> -Cresoxy-		134-36°, 138.2-138.7°	166.68	166
5. <i>o</i> -Nitrophenoxy-		156.5°, 158.2-158.5°	197.85	197
6. <i>m</i> -Nitrophenoxy-		151-54.5°, 156.4-156.7°	195.8	197
7. <i>p</i> -Nitrophenoxy-		184°, 187.2-187.5°	196.25	197
8. <i>o</i> -Chlorophenoxy-		143-45°, 147.2-147.7°	186	186.5
9. <i>m</i> -Chlorophenoxy-		108-10°, 109.7-110.2°	185.2	186.5
10. <i>p</i> -Chlorophenoxy-		156.7-157.2°, 155-156.5°	185.6	186.5
11. α -Naphthoxy-		191-92°	200.5	202
12. β -Naphthoxy-		153-54.5°	201	202
13. <i>o</i> -Xylenoxy-	161-62°	—	181.82	180
14. <i>m</i> -Xylenoxy-	111°	—	181.50	180
15. Guaisoxy-		121.4°	181.68	182
16. Thymoxy-		148-49°	206.9	208
17. <i>p</i> -Iodophenoxy-		154-56°, 159.5-60°	276.8	277.93
18. β -Phenoxy-propionic acid	96-97°	—	166.8	166
19. β - <i>o</i> -Cresoxy		94.5°	180.8	180
20. β -Guaisoxy-	134-35°	—	195.66	196
21. <i>o</i> -Nitrophenoxy-		121-22°	210.02	211
22. <i>p</i> -Nitrophenoxy-		118-19°	211.83	211

Mercuration of Aryloxy-fatty Acids.—The following mixtures of solutions were heated on a water-bath until a test portion became entirely soluble in alkali (about 4-6 hours):—

(a) One mol. of yellow mercuric oxide in sufficient 50% acetic acid to dissolve it, and one mol. of aryloxy-fatty acid in 50% alcoholic solution.

(b) Equimolecular amounts of mercuric oxide and aryloxy-fatty acid in aqueous medium were heated on a water-bath with occasional stirring till the yellow colour changed to white.

(c) Equimolecular quantities of mercuric acetate in water and aryloxy-fatty acid in dilute acetic acid solution.

(d) HgO , freshly precipitated from HgCl_2 , was mixed with an alkaline solution of the aryloxy fatty acid.

In (a), (b) and (c), the products were separated as powdery substance and in (d) dilution with water and acidification with dilute acetic acid were required. The phenoxy and cresoxy compounds were formed easily within 45 minutes, chloro compounds required at least an hour, while xylenoxy compound came out almost immediately. To obtain the compound of α -naphthoxyacetic acid heating was controlled between 60° and 70° for 30 minutes; the filtration and subsequent purification being done very quickly. Longer heating and exposure to light and air made the compound dark in colour. *p*-Nitrophenoxypropionic acid derivative came out with a small yield after 6 hours' heating and on pouring the mixture in a large volume of cold water and after standing overnight.

An attempt was made to mercurate them with mercuric chloride, but it failed.

Purification.—The substances were dissolved in dilute alkali and were reprecipitated either by dilute acetic acid or by CO_2 , or a solution of the substance in hot glacial acetic acid was poured in a large volume of cold water. The precipitate was filtered, washed with hot water, boiled with alcohol and filtered hot and dried.

General Properties.—All the compounds are insoluble in water, in dilute acids and in most organic solvents, but are soluble in glacial acetic acid. They are easily soluble in dilute alkali. Conc. HCl decomposes them to mercuric chloride and the corresponding aryloxy-fatty acid. From solutions of the compounds in KI , by adding requisite amount of dilute H_2SO_4 , iodo-mercury compounds may be formed. The compounds dissolve in iodine in KI , but break down on the addition of H_2SO_4 to mercuric iodide and iodo-phenoxyacetic acid. The methyl ester of hydroxymercuriphenoxyacetic acid can be easily obtained. Cu , Zn , Fe , Ni and Al salts are easily thrown down, being insoluble. They are also insoluble in dilute HCl , but break down when boiled with HCl to insoluble phenoxyacetic acid, HgCl_2 and the metallic chloride. Almost all of the compounds are stable to ammonium sulphide and hydrogen sulphide at the ordinary temperatures.

*Mercuration of Phenylglycine-*o*-carboxylic Acid.*—Anthranilic acid (13.6 g.), chloroacetic acid (11.4 g.) and sodium carbonate (anhyd., 17 g.) in 100 c.c. water were heated on a water-bath for 3 hours, cooled, and acidified with dilute HCl . A light brown precipitate of phenylglycine-*o*-carboxylic acid was obtained, which was filtered next day, recrystallised from water to get colorless crystals, m.p. 209° .

The mono- and diacetoxymercury compounds were prepared from HgO and dilute acetic acid; the nitro compounds with mercuric nitrate in aqueous solution and the Cl-Hg compounds were prepared by the method of Neogi and Chatterjee (this *Journal*, 1928, 5, 221) by HgCl₂ in presence of sodium bicarbonate; use of glycerol was not necessary here. All the compounds are insoluble in water, in acids and in most organic solvents, but are soluble in alkali.

The equivalents of the compounds were determined and Hg was estimated by Whitmore's gold crucible method (Whitmore, "Organic Compounds of Mercury," p. 365, 1921) and chlorine was determined by Piria and Schiff's method. The results of the analysis show that in all cases mono-mercurated anhydride of aryloxy-fatty acids, were formed.

Bacterical Tests.—The Rideal Walker Drop method (*Lancet*, 1909, ii, 1516; *J. Roy. Sant. Inst.*, 1903, 424) was followed in determining the bactericidal action of the compounds prepared. The results are shown in Table III and Table IV.

TABLE IV
Analysis of the mercury compounds.

Name of derivatives.	M p.	Equiv.		% Hg.		% Chlorine	
		Calc.	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.
1. C ₆ H ₄ (-O-CH ₂ COO)-Hg	230° (decomp.)	350	351.5	57.1	56.55		
2. CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃ (-O-CH ₂ COO)-Hg (o)	243° (brown)	364	365.2	54.8	55		
3. CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃ (-O-CH ₂ COO)-Hg (m)	200-202° black	364	364.8	51.8	55.2		
4. CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃ (-O-CH ₂ COO)-Hg (p)	158° (brown)	364	351.92	54.8	53.9		
5. NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ (-O-CH ₂ COO)-Hg (o)	215° (decomp.)	395	—	50.6	51		
6. NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ (-O-CH ₂ COO)-Hg (m)	162° (brown liq.)	395	—	50.6	49.8		
7. NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ (-O-CH ₂ COO)-Hg (p)	181° (,,)	95	—	50.6	51.81		
8. Cl-C ₆ H ₃ (-O-CH ₂ COO)-Hg (o)	215° (decomp.)	384.5	385.6	52	51.68		
9. Cl-C ₆ H ₃ (O-CH ₂ COO)-Hg (m)	215° (,,)	381.5	383.9	52	51.05		
10. Cl-C ₆ H ₃ (O-CH ₂ COO)-Hg (p)	217° (brown)	384.5	384.85	52	52.8		
11. C ₁₀ H ₆ (O-CH ₂ COO)-Hg (α)	230-32° (black)	400	398.82	50	48.6		
12. C ₁₀ H ₆ (-O-CH ₂ COO)-Hg (β)	204° (decomp.)	400	400.65	50	49.1		
13. (CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ (-O-CH ₂ COO)-Hg (o)	26° (brown)	379	378.5	52.7	51.92		
14. (CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ (-O-CH ₂ COO)-Hg (m)	140° (liq.)	379	378.81	52.7	51.36		
15. CH ₃ O-C ₆ H ₃ (O-CH ₂ COO)-Hg	222° (brown)	390	381.4	52.63	52.9		
16. (CH ₃ -CH-C ₆ H ₇ -O-CH ₂ COO)-Hg	232° (,,)	406	406.58	49.3	50.01		
17. I-C ₆ H ₃ (O-CH ₂ COO)-Hg (p)	251-52° (decomp.)	475.9	474.86	42.01	41.05		
18. C ₆ H ₄ (-O-CH ₂ -CH ₂ COO)-Hg (β)	194-96° (brown)	364	364.86	54.8	53.1		
19. CH ₃ (C ₆ H ₃ (-O-CH ₂ -CH ₂ COO)-Hg (o)	232° (brown)	378	379.29	52.9	51.82		
20. CH ₃ O-C ₆ H ₃ (O-CH ₂ -CH ₂ COO)-Hg	151° (decomp.)	394	393.05	50.76	51.6		
21. NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ (O-CH ₂ -CH ₂ COO)-Hg (o)	210° (,,)	409	—	48.89	49.45		
22. NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ (O-CH ₂ -CH ₂ COO)-Hg (p)	235°	409	—	48.89	47.62		
23. Acetoxy-Hg-phenylglycine- <i>o</i> -carboxylic acid	210°	437	—	45.76	45.14		
24. Diacetoxy-,, ,	225°	679	—	58.91	58.01		
25. Chloro-,, ,	236°	429.5	—	46.56	47.03	8.26	8.75
26. Dichloro-,, ,	196-98°	664	—	60.24	59.86	12.71	10.18
27. Nitro-,, ,	215°	456	—	43.85	44.03	—	—